

THE EVOLUTION OF ENGLISH AS A RECEPTIVE SPEECH LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This article's objective is to show teachers how to retain the exercises so well that they may use them with their students, modifying the tasks to fit the students' abilities. More crucially, it spreads the myth that teachers' professional development is dependent on obtaining new knowledge and resources from other sources, which discourages teachers from feeling in control of their own professional development.

Keywords: materials development, autonomy, methodology workshops, communicative activity, cultural contexts, professional development, transferable.

INTRODUCTION

The development of receptive speech competence in the systematization of specialized educational materials on the basis of methodical support of English language teaching and development of professional competence and linguo-didactic analysis is highlighted.

Introducing differentiated education according to the direction and level of students' mastery of academic subjects or their creative abilities, firstly, to further develop the capabilities of gifted children during the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities; secondly, not to waste their time; thirdly, it allows to ensure the moderation of the relationship between students.

On the basis of differentiated education, each teacher is required to be able to fully realize the inner potential of gifted students, to contribute to the formation of creative qualities in them. The creative abilities of the students of the educational institution are achieved by focusing the attention of the team of the educational institution on a single goal, as well as by actively involving the public in this process.

[6, 10]

By differentiated we mean a system of education in which each student has the right and guarantee to focus preferentially on his or her pursuits with a minimal level of general education under constantly changing living conditions. Differentiation of education is especially important in relation to English, which is one of the school subjects, because the English language consists of information directly related to things and events in the real world, with their inter-ethnic tolerance, mutual respect, appreciation of the customs of other nations and their language. depends.

The essence of the professional classification of the teaching process in different programs is to take into account the psychological and psychophysiological characteristics of the students in order to develop them to the maximum extent in the chosen fields.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It is important to determine the basic level of general secondary education in the period of stratification of education, formation of its multi-specialized structure, clarification of educational goals and levels that are important for all students, guaranteeing the possibility of continuing education in higher educational institutions regardless of the future professional interests of students, regardless of the direction of education.

Specific goals of educational methods differ from each other, that is: to increase independent, creative cognitive activities of students; creating a structure of the educational process that is as close as possible to the characteristics of a person's feelings; adapt the educational content to the individual needs of the person and the level of his basic preparation; development of interests and abilities of a person; creating favorable conditions for students to realize their inclinations, interests and abilities; organization of student activity; ensuring that the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities is in the description of personal activity is properly distributed in academic lyceums and vocational colleges.

The methodology of teaching foreign languages is divided into general and private methodology. The general methodology discusses the principles of education that apply to all foreign languages. "General methodology of teaching foreign languages in secondary school", published under the editorship of I.V. Rakhmonov, V.S. Tsetlin and translated into Uzbek, R.A. Zaripova's "Guide to foreign language teaching methodology", J. Jalalov's "Foreign language teaching methodology" can be considered as a general methodology. Private methodology deals with the issue

of teaching one foreign language. This includes "Methods of teaching English" by G.V. Rogova, O.Kh. Hoshimov, I.Ya. Examples are Yakubov's "English language teaching methodology", S.F. Shatilov's "Metodika obucheniya nemetskomu yazyku v sredney shkole".

The main task of pedagogues is to train specialists who can adapt to the changing production conditions at the level of world requirements, not to recognize the amount of information given as the main factor in this process, but to form a creative approach to them and educate the qualities of independent thinking.

Improving the quality of English language teaching in non-philological higher education institutions is directly related to the following factors:

- 1) increase in the need for highly qualified new generation specialists who know the English language;
- 2) low level of English literacy of first-year students admitted to a higher education institution;
- 3) students' mastery of communicative competences specific to different languages at different levels;
- 4) Inadequacy of educational literature aimed at ensuring the educational-methodical individuality of students in mastering communicative competences specific to another language, etc.

The search for effective ways to improve the quality of the English language teaching process in non-philological higher education institutions is being carried out in different directions at the same time. In English language courses of non-philological higher education institutions, the main goal is to prepare students for speech activity in a goal-oriented manner in connection with the professional and social spheres of communication. While the authors are developing programs related to different directions, the sole goal is to teach the speech skills specific to a foreign language, which are defined by S.K. Lelyushkina as "non-standard solutions, learning complex words, unusual speech tools, acquiring methods, and shaping thinking." mastery provision is determined.

In non-philological higher education institutions, contextual and professional-oriented education is reflected as the generally accepted directions of English language teaching. As a basic concept of vocationally oriented education, the context is of great importance in the formation of students' linguistic readiness in connection with the future specialty. In order to determine the communicative indicators of

improving the quality of English language teaching in non-philological higher education institutions, it is necessary to clarify the essence of the concepts of "quality", "teaching quality", "teaching quality parameters". [1, 7]

F. Saidova, who studied the issue of quality management of foreign language teaching in technical higher education institutions, did not conduct separate research on quality parameters and indicators, but interpreted the features related to its management in the following way: "Educational quality management" to ensure adaptation, to the conditions of educational processes reach and support, its implementation and its results are understood. Not this or that element of the educational process, but the characteristics of these elements, their compliance with certain norms, should be managed. But the most accurate and complete definition of this phenomenon is based on the idea of managing the quality of education through the results aimed at regulating the quality indicators of the educational process.

Therefore, in order to develop the creative activity of students of non-philological higher educational institutions in the process of learning foreign languages and evaluate the quality of teaching, it is necessary to implement the following conditions:

- to create a communicative-educational environment;
- to increase motivation of students in the educational process;
- developing students' creative activity;
- constant use of modern interactive methods and technologies in educational sessions;
- conducting training sessions in classrooms equipped with a set of didactic tools;
- Availability of stages of development of creative activity of students of non-philological higher educational institutions.

How to apply modern strategies that are important in the development of receptive speech skills and the expected result of them will help the student in the course of the monograph. During the research of the monograph, scientific works (books and articles) of a number of scientists on this topic were studied in order to form integrated receptive skills in the student.

DISCUSSION

Philosophical and scientific-pedagogical approach to the researched problem, using a set of methods compatible with the purpose, object, subject, tasks of the

monograph, the number of higher education institutions involved in the experiment is at the required level, the results of the experiment are based on statistical data and processed mathematically and statistically and the content of the works published on the topic, as well as a systematic and consistent approach to the problem of the monograph, the results of experiments and their compliance with the modern requirements for pedagogical monographs, ensure the reliability of the monograph results.

It is also important to pay attention to psychological factors in language learning in the formation of integrated speech skills. It is known that the effectiveness of the educational process is directly related to the interest in the result of the work that motivates students to perform certain activities. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account subjective factors when choosing lexical exercises. In addition, the age-related differences in thinking, thinking and memorization of language learners are definitely taken into account in this selection. In the scientific literature, it is noted that among the psychological characteristics that each young person develops, it is important to distinguish the main connection between all the psychological qualities of the student at the stage of formation: [5, 12]

1) In continuing education, great attention is paid to the level of personal interest and interest of the students in learning a foreign language in relation to the learning material and the educational activities being performed;

2) it is emphasized that thinking takes a leading place in the development of memory, that is, the priority of logical memory retention over mechanical memorization.

In this article, senior teacher of Fergana Polytechnic Institute "Uzbek language and language teaching" department 13.00.02 independent researcher in the specialty "Theory and Methodology of Education and Training" (English) Nazaralieva Matlyubakhan Anarjanovna on the topic "Formation of integrated receptive skills in teaching English" The results of the dissertation research prepared for obtaining the scientific degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) during the 2022-2023 academic years, experimental work was carried out with students of Fergana State University in non-philological fields (students of German and French language fields). 56 students participated in the organization of experimental work. From this, 29 students were selected as experimental group and 27 students as control group.

Based on this, in the development of students' professional competence in foreign languages, the formation of receptive speech skills in English, the modernization of innovative activities related to the use of modern pedagogical technologies, the gradual formation of receptive skills with a differential approach to reading and listening techniques and other types of speech, linguo-didactic and psychological factors determine the effect;

- Analyzing the development of receptive speech competence in the teaching of the English language and the development of professional competence on the basis of methodical support and linguo didactic analysis on the systematization of specialized educational materials;

- Use of interactive methods and technology of didactic games in formation and development of integrated receptive speech competence;

- Application of the technique of appropriate application of various strategies in the formation of integrated reading skills;

- Development of methods of formation of receptive speech competence of Uzbek students in English based on the requirements and principles of the communicative method.

During the trial period, he benefited from an English audio-textbook based on the TPRS (Teaching Proficiency through Reading and Storytelling) methodology, which was created in the educational process using an innovative method of teaching. This book takes into account students' interest and passion for learning English. During the experiment, special attention was paid to such factors as determining the ways and methods of eliminating imbalances.

The following results obtained as part of M.A. Nazaralieva's Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation were applied to the educational process of the institute:

With TPRS, teachers promote language skills among students through children's novels, engaging stories, and interactive materials that are contextual, repetitive, and understandable. Or when explained simply, the teacher uses stories that are understandable and interesting, as we mentioned above, in the course of the lesson. [1, 2]

The teacher starts telling the story at an important, noteworthy point and asks many questions to the class: a) to ensure that the class understands the language;

b) adding personal, interesting and understandable details to the story. Students read mostly stories created in class, but also stories created by other classes, stories written by individual students, advertisements and articles from magazines and newspapers, children's books, and short novels written for TPRS classes. In short, TPRS consists of telling, listening to, and conducting short and simple question-and-answer sessions on a variety of stories that include natural phrases, commonly used words, and idioms. This increased students' interest in learning English.

Initial condition					
Ball	"5"	"4"	"3"	"2"	Total students
Experience group	10	12	30	54	106
Control group	8	10	36	52	106
Total score	18	12	66	106	212
Final condition					
Ball	"5"	"4"	"3"	"2"	Total students
Experience group	20	22	10	54	106
Control group	12	12	30	52	106
Total score	32	34	40	106	212

In Table 1 a_{1i} : ($i = 1,2,3,4$) suitable respectively "5", "4", "3", "2" points received experience in the group of students average the number means $_b_{2i}$: ($i = 1,2,3,4$) suitable respectively "5", "4", "3", "2" points received control in the group of students average the number means $_$ Based on Table 1 initial in case experience and control in groups average monitoring is determined.

$$X_r = \frac{5 \cdot 10 + 4 \cdot 12 + 3 \cdot 30 + 2 \cdot 54}{106} = \frac{296}{106} \approx 2.8$$

$$X_n = \frac{5 \cdot 8 + 4 \cdot 10 + 3 \cdot 36 + 2 \cdot 52}{106} = \frac{292}{106} \approx 2.7$$

So both the group indicators initial in case $X_r \approx 2.8$, $X_n \approx 2.7$ is equal to Based on Table 1 final in the case average score indicators is calculated as:

$$X_r = \frac{5 \cdot 20 + 4 \cdot 22 + 3 \cdot 10 + 2 \cdot 54}{106} = \frac{326}{106} \approx 3$$

$$X_n = \frac{5 \cdot 12 + 4 \cdot 12 + 3 \cdot 30 + 2 \cdot 52}{106} = \frac{292}{106} \approx 2.8$$

So, $X_r > X_n (3 > 2.8)$ control to the group relatively experience of the group growth percentage determined:

$$\frac{X_r}{X_n} * 100\% - 100\% = 120\% - 100\% = 20\%$$

Experience results average efficiency of 20% gave that make a guess (hypothesis). can _

In that case head hypothesis

$$H_0: P_{1i} \neq P_{2i} \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

All categories the alternative hypothesis H_1 for is as follows:

$$H_1: P_{1i} = P_{2i} \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

Four from the category never when not one for.

Statistical testing of the hypothesis for below criteria (symptom) is used:

$$T = \frac{1}{n_1 * n_2} \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{(n_1 b_{2i} - n_2 a_{1i})^2}{a_{1i} + b_{2i}}$$

T is random quantity (statistics) of distribution χ^2 to the law tall breaks and freedom level $J = 3$ to equal to

Hypothesis check in the rule value as follows level χ^2 the critical points from the table $V = 3$ when χ^2 critical point found, based on Table 1 (1). observed value $T_{qiyamat}$ is found. After $\chi_{1,2}$ and $T_{qiyamat}$ compared, If

$$T_{qiyamat} > \chi_{1,2}$$

inequality if fulfilled, a value level H_0 hypothesis refuse will be done and H_1 hypothesis acceptance will be done. On the contrary

$$T_{qiyamat} < \chi_{1,2}$$

if H_0 hypothesis acceptance will be done.

Now to the rule basically $\chi_{1,2}$ from the table we find Let $\alpha = 0.05$. He is alone χ^2 critical points from the table $J = 3$ we find in:

$$\chi_{1-0.05} = \chi_{0.95} = 7.815$$

$T_{qiyamat}(1)$ based on the formula and Table 1 we calculate:

$$T_{qiyamat} = \frac{1}{n_1 n_2} \left[\frac{(n_1 b_{21} - n_2 a_{11})^2}{a_{11} + b_{21}} + \frac{(n_1 b_{22} - n_2 a_{12})^2}{a_{12} + b_{22}} + \frac{(n_1 b_{23} - n_2 a_{13})^2}{a_{13} + b_{23}} + \frac{(n_1 b_{24} - n_2 a_{14})^2}{a_{14} + b_{24}} \right] =$$

$$\frac{1}{106 * 106} \left[\frac{(106 * 12 - 106 * 20)^2}{32} + \frac{(106 * 12 - 106 * 22)^2}{34} + \frac{(106 * 30 - 106 * 10)^2}{40} + \frac{(106 * 52 - 106 * 54)^2}{106} \right] = \frac{1}{11236} (22472 + 33047 + 112360 + 424) = \frac{168303}{11236} \approx 14.98$$

So, $T_{qiymat} \approx 14.98$ and $T_{qiymat} > x_{0.95}$ ($14.98 > 7.815$)

In conclusion according to, H_1 accept the hypothesis is done, H_0 the hypothesis is rejected.

So, scientific pedagogic experience results average knowledge of 20% effect gave is calculated as in case in practice to apply recommendation will be done. [8, 12]

CONCLUSION

Researcher M.A. Nazaralieva's scientific-methodological recommendations developed on the basis of the results of her dissertation, the efficiency of the innovative approach was determined by comparative analysis of the traditional teaching and the innovative approach in higher education institutions. The formation of the speech mechanism, the theory of speech activity, the psychological features of learning the language as a means of communication formed the psychological basis of this study. Observation of the educational process, effective use of reading and listening strategies and conversation with students helped to identify, analyze and develop ways to overcome psychological difficulties in the process of formation of receptive speech skills (not knowing orthographic rules, fear of making mistakes, lack of motivation).

On the basis of these psychological characteristics, a logically based educational activity is created, which is useful for the student in mastering foreign lexicon. It is important for students to try to systematize their knowledge in acquiring vocabulary. Scientists have emphasized the need to pay special attention to the formation of the skill of striving to put the acquired knowledge into a certain system in the educational process. In fact, students are not completely satisfied with the amount of knowledge they have mastered, that is, information in the direction of events, and they feel the need to expand, supplement and organize their knowledge. Two important conclusions can be drawn from the opinions expressed: the educational material should be provided as complete as required, including all the necessary information; and the educational activities of students should be directed to their complete and systematic information acquisition.

One of the main requirements of the modern approach to the lesson is that it is important not only to use texts in the lesson, but also to acquaint the students with the literature of the country where the language is being studied. In addition, it is important to show the students a video film related to the topic and to know their

opinions about this film. In this case, students should describe their impressions of the film and/or a summary of the film. Speaking about other films similar to the film also has a positive effect on the development of speaking skills in them.

How to organize and conduct a lesson depends on the skills and experience of the teacher. A modern approach to the lesson and the effective use of new pedagogical methods during the lesson will also depend on the teachers' interest in their subject and their desire for innovations. [10, 12]

Therefore, preparation for each lesson and modern approaches to lessons will make the teacher and the student not bored during the lesson, and the lessons will be organized effectively. These approaches allow students to develop language skills and, of course, become fluent in the language they are learning.

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